

X-ray Diffraction Study on Chromium Oxide Calcination Processes

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The various phases and transformation temperature occurring in the different Cr_2O_3 calcination process has been determined by X-ray diffraction. Six series of chromium salts were selected for calcination processes. The analysis showed that the conversion from CrO_3 to $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ goes through a series of intermediate oxides. The decomposition of ammonium dichromate and ammonium chromate is spontaneous. Chromium acetate decomposes slowly. Amorphous chromium oxide hydroxide does not produce a crystalline perior to transformation to $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$. The crystallite size and surface area of the final $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ product obtained from various sources were measured. It has been suggested that ammonium dichromate may be a suitable chromium salt where mechanical mixing process is followed in the preparation of a catalyst containing $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$.

THE structural characteristics of solids are influenced by the methods of preparations and chemical composition¹⁻³. The calcination process during the preparation of a solid generally used as an effective tool for attributing the desired specific structural and textural character to the residual products⁴⁻⁷.

Chromium(III) oxide ($\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$) is widely used as an active phase or as a promoter in a variety of mixed oxide⁸⁻¹² catalysts. It is also an important carrier material for its stable surface at high temperature. Different chromium salts have been used as a starting material for the preparation of chromium(III) oxide¹³⁻¹⁶. So far the systematic studies regarding phase transformation during calcination processes have been reported only for chromium (III) oxide gel and chromates¹⁷⁻²⁰. Some references are also available in the literature regarding the calcination of CrO_3 ^{21,22} under high oxygen pressure or in vacuum because of their importance in synthesizing CrO_3 as a ferromagnetic component. A knowledge of the various phases and transformation temperature occurring in the different chromium oxide calcination processes may be helpful in the selection of a chromium compound in the preparation of a catalyst containing chromium oxide. With this end in view, the present investigation has been carried out to characterise the heat treated products obtained after various calcining conditions, evaluate the optimum condition of the calcination process for different chromium compounds, determine the crystallite size and surface area of the final chromic oxide product. Attempts have also been made to assess the suitability of different chromium salts for the preparation of an active catalyst.

Experimental

For the calcination purpose, (i) chromium (VI) oxide, (ii) chromium(III) nitrate and chromium(III) acetate have been studied. For phase transformation studies 5g of each chromium compound in powder

form were taken in a porcelain crucible and heated in a tubular furnace at different times and temperatures as mentioned in respective tables. For comparative physical parameters studies, Cr_2O_3 has also been prepared from chromic oxide gel and ammonium chromate by heating the respective salts at 450° and 400° for 4 hr and in the case of ammonium dichromate, it has calcined at 200° for 2 hr. All the reagents were AnalaR grade.

X-ray diffraction analysis: X-ray powder photographs of the original starting material and the calcined specimens of each series were taken in a standard Guiner camera using crystal reflected monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation X-ray tube being operated at 40 KV and 20 mA. The phases were determined by comparing the observed patterns with standard ASTM patterns²³.

The crystallite size of $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ prepared from different chromium compounds was determined by line broadening method using the Scherrer formula²⁴.

The crystallite size measurements were performed by scanning the diffraction line (2.66Å, 104 plane) of $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ on the Philips X-ray diffractometer, PW 1050/5. The sample in each series calcined at the temperature at which the decomposition is complete in that particular system, was taken for crystallite size and surface area measurements.

Surface area measurements. Specific surface area of the calcined samples were determined by nitrogen adsorption at liquid nitrogen temperature using BET equation²⁵.

Results

The different phases present in the samples obtained by calcining (i) chromium(VI) oxide, (ii) chromium nitrate, (iii) chromium acetate at different temperatures and periods are given in Tables 1 to 3. The crystallite size and surface area data are shown in Table 4.

Phase transformation

Chromium(VI) oxide. It can be seen from Table 1 that the conversion from CrO_3 to Cr_2O_3 takes place between 400° to 425° for the calcination period of 4 hr. It is also evident from Table 1, that the conversion from CrO_3 to $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ can be completed at lower temperature if the duration of calcination is more. This indicates that the calcination process is a slow one and the calcination at lower temperature favours the formation of higher valent oxides as intermediate products in an indefinite proportion. These intermediate oxide phases as seen in Table 1

TABLE IA. CALCINATION OF CrO_3 IN AIR

Sl. No.	Calcination temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$	Calcination period (hrs)	Phases present
1.	R.T.	-	CrO_3
2.	250	4	Cr_3O_8 , Cr_2O_5 , CrO_3 (trace)
3.	300	4	Cr_2O_5 , Cr_3O_8 , Cr_3O_4
4.	350	4	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 , Cr_3O_4

are Cr_3O_8 , Cr_2O_5 , Cr_3O_4 and CrO_2 . The main course of decomposition of CrO_3 to the final product Cr_2O_3

takes place in a stepwise manner according to the following scheme. $\text{CrO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Cr}_3\text{O}_8 \rightarrow \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_5 \rightarrow \text{Cr}_3\text{O}_4 \rightarrow \text{CrO}_2 \rightarrow \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$.

Chromium nitrate. Table 2 indicates that $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ decomposes above 200° . Although initially it is in poorly crystalline state with a minor amount of Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 phases but around 400° the product is $\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and well crystalline in nature.

TABLE 2. CHROMIUM ACETATE CALCINATION SERIES IN AIR

Sl. No.	Calcination temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Calcination period (hrs)	Phases present
1	R.T.	-	Amorphous phase.
2.	250	4	-do-
3.	300	4	-do-
4.	350	4	Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_5 (minor)
5.	400	2	Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_5 (trace)
6.	400	4	Cr_2O_3
7.	450	2	Cr_2O_3

Chromium acetate. It can be seen from the Table 3 that chromium acetate is amorphous in nature

TABLE IB. CALCINATION OF CrO_3 IN AIR

Duration of calcination in hrs.	Crystal phase composition at the respective calcination / temperature			
	375°	400°	425°	450°
$\frac{1}{2}$	Cr_3O_8 , Cr_2O_5 CrO_2 (trace)	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 Cr_2O_3 (trace)	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2
1	Cr_3O_8 , Cr_2O_5 CrO_2 (trace)	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 Cr_2O_3 (minor)	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2
2	Cr_2O_5 , Cr_3O_8 CrO_2	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2 (trace)	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2 (trace)
3	Cr_2O_5 , Cr_3O_8 CrO_2 , Cr_2O_3 (trace)	Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_5 CrO_2	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
4	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 , Cr_3O_8 , Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2 (trace)	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
5	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
6	Cr_2O_5 , CrO_2 Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
7	Cr_2O_5 , Cr_2O_3 CrO_2	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
10	Cr_2O_5 , Cr_2O_3 , CrO_2	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
14	Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2O_5	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
18	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3
22	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3	Cr_2O_3

TABLE 3. CHROMIUM NITRATE CALCINATION SERIES IN AIR

Sl. No.	Calcination temperature (°C)	Calcination period (hrs)	Phases present
1.	R.T.	-	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O
2.	250	4	Cr ₂ O ₃ , Cr ₂ O ₅ , CrO ₂ (trace)
3.	300	4	Cr ₂ O ₃ , CrO ₂ (trace)
4.	350	2	Cr ₂ O ₃
5.	400	2	Cr ₂ O ₃

upto 300°. It begins to decompose above 300° and the conversion to α -Cr₂O₃ is complete around 400° for 4 hr. The formation of intermediate oxide is noticed only in minor amount at 350°.

that ammonium dichromate can be used economically for the mixed oxide catalyst preparation where the percentage of chromia to be used is not high. It has been noticed that ammonium dichromate can be prepared *in situ*, by the interaction of equivalent amount of ammonium carbonate with chromium (VI) oxide during kneading process in case of mixed oxide catalyst. The formation of (NH₄)₂Cr₂O₇ *in situ*, makes the parent catalytic mass porous (honey-comb structure) due to the evolution of carbon dioxide from the interaction of (NH₄)₂CO₃ with CrO₃²⁷.

Amorphous chromium(III) oxide hydroxide which is precipitated from nitrate solution can also be used for mechanical mixing process. But it is necessary to calcine the hydrated chromium(III) oxide at 450° for obtaining the crystalline α -Cr₂O₃, though the dehydration of the gel completes around 250°²⁸. Chromium acetate is another suitable organic salt

 Table 4. Crystallite size and surface area of α -Cr₂O₃

Sl. No.	Source	Calcination temperature (°C)	Calcination period (hrs)	Crystallite size (Å)	Surface area
1.	Chromium (VI) oxide	400	6	550	22.55
2.	Ammonium dichromate	260	2	280	26.42
3.	Ammonium chromate	400	4	420	20.12
4.	Chromium acetate	400	4	150	21.1
5.	Chromium nitrate	400	4	430	24.55
6.	Hydrate chromium (III) Oxide	450	4	250	30.60

Discussion

It may be worthwhile to discuss the suitability of different chromium salts as a starting material for the preparation of Cr₂O₃ in the light of the results discussed above.

For catalytic process, chromium(VI) oxide is one of the cheapest sources for preparing α -Cr₂O₃ (specially when mechanical mixing process is favourable for mixed oxide catalysts). But due to the high decomposition temperature of CrO₃, it may not be a suitable starting material for the preparation of a mixed oxide catalyst containing other components having low calcination temperature. For mixed oxide catalytic system it is desirable to keep the calcination temperature in lower region for maintaining favourable physical parameters of the catalytic mass. But if CrO₃ is incorporated in mixed oxide catalyst then it should be calcined above 400° for complete conversion into α -Cr₂O₃. In the case of ammonium dichromate, it has been reported that the decomposition is quite spontaneous and occurs at a moderate temperature (200°-250°)²⁶. As the decomposition is a spontaneous one, the duration of calcination is not a factor at all. It seems therefore

which may be used in mechanical mixing process for catalyst preparation. But its decomposition is not rapid and requires to calcine it at a comparatively higher temperature for a prolonged period, in order to convert into crystalline α -Cr₂O₃. Further, due to high cost of the material its use may not be economical for all cases.

It can be seen from Table 4 that the crystallite size of α -Cr₂O₃ obtained by calcination of hydrated chromic (III) oxide and ammonium dichromate are lowest compared to that obtained from other sources. The finer crystallite size not only helps for better dispersion of the component in the bulk material but contributes a greater surface to the final catalytic mass. The well dispersed mass also provides a better thermal stability to the catalytic mass where chromia acts as a structural promoter, as has been reported elsewhere.^{29,30}

The crystallite size of α -Cr₂O₃ obtained from different sources follows in the order: hydrated chromium (III) oxide < ammonium dichromate < ammonium chromate < chromium nitrate < chromic (VI) oxide < chromium acetate. The crystallite size of Cr₂O₃ obtained by calcination of chromium acetate is

maximum. Although some other organic salts favour the formation of smaller particles, yet the acetate salts are not very much helpful. Not only chromium acetate, but also copper acetate and zinc acetate show a similar trend to form higher crystallite sizes in their respective oxides according to our experience. Hygroscopicity of the calcined product obtained from chromium acetate may be one of the causes for its higher crystallite size. This has also been observed by Bartram in the case of BeO calcination process³¹. The calcination product of the amorphous chromium (III) oxide hydroxide shows lowest crystallite size.

From the line broadening measurements the crystallite size growth of α -Cr₂O₃ obtained from different sources has been measured and reported elsewhere²⁹. The crystallite sizes were determined along the direction perpendicular to the planes, 104, 110 and 116. An anisotropic crystal growth of α -Cr₂O₃ has been observed. In all the samples a definite tendency of crystal growth perpendicular to the 104 planes is observed.

Surface area measurements of the crystalline α -Cr₂O₃ obtained from different sources do not differ very much. The rapid diminution of surface area to a minimum value on crystallisation has been reported by different workers²⁸. The surface area measurements of α -Cr₂O₃ obtained from different sources in the present investigation also supports the earlier views.

Considering all the aspects, as discussed above, it appears that chromium(III) oxide gel and ammonium dichromate is more favourable as a suitable source of Cr₂O₃ where mechanical mixing process is followed for the dispersion of structural promoter over parent materials as well as to reduce the calcination temperature of the mixed oxide system used as catalyst. It is also reported by Oliver²² that the use of ammonium dichromate as a source of Cr₂O₃ in the Cu-Cr-Zn oxide catalyst, enhanced the activity of catalyst. He has also shown that the pyrolysis method is quite suitable and easier in the preparation of mixed oxide catalyst. The suitability of chromic (III) oxide gel as a starting material for preparing active catalyst is well established.

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